

Graph-Based Multi-Face Deepfake Detection via CNN Feature Embeddings and Attention Networks

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Abstract Deepfake detection methods commonly rely on single-face analysis, overlooking relational cues among multiple faces in an image. We propose a graph-based framework for multi-face deepfake detection that explicitly models interactions between faces. Faces are detected with YOLOv8 and represented as graph nodes, with CNN embeddings providing feature representations. Relational dependencies are captured via Graph Neural Networks, including attention-based and aggregation-based architectures. Systematic evaluation across multiple CNN backbones shows that attention-based GNNs consistently outperform aggregation-based approaches, with EfficientNet-B0 offering the best balance between performance and generalization. Experiments on Deepfake-and-Real-Images, and cross-dataset evaluations demonstrate significant improvements in accuracy, recall, and F1-score, confirming the effectiveness of relational graph modeling for robust multi-face deepfake detection in realistic scenarios.

Key words Deepfake detection, GNN, Multi-face analysis, CNN embeddings, Graph Attention Networks.

1 Introduction

Recent advances in deep learning have enabled realistic deepfakes, which pose serious threats such as misinformation and identity fraud. Robust and generalizable detection methods are therefore crucial.

Most existing deepfake detectors rely on CNNs and assume a single face per image, processing each face independently. However, real-world images and videos often contain multiple faces, each potentially with a different authenticity state,

creating challenges like variable face counts, heterogeneous labels, and intra-image dependencies (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Examples of fake images from the Deepfake-and-Real-Images dataset illustrating the multi-face challenge.

To address these limitations, this work formulates multi-face deepfake detection as a graph learning problem, representing faces as nodes and their relationships as edges. By integrating CNN embeddings with Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), the model captures relational information and enables collective reasoning across multiple faces, moving beyond independent face-level classification.

2 Related Work

Existing deepfake detection research mainly leverages **CNNs (Convolutional Neural Networks)** to extract discriminative facial features. For instance, Sârbu et al. [6] propose a lightweight four-layer CNN achieving 97.5% accuracy on the *Deepfake and Real Images* dataset, but it is limited to single-face images and does not model inter-face interactions.

Other studies [1],[5] apply CNN pipelines to cropped facial regions, confirming their effectiveness for detecting forged content; however, they treat each face independently, reducing performance in multi-face scenarios. Sharma [7] uses transfer learning with VGG16 and ResNet50, enhanced by ensemble models, achieving high accuracy but still focusing on individual face analysis.

General limitation: most approaches consider faces in isolation and do not capture relationships between multiple faces in an image or video.

3 Proposed Method

We present a unified multi-face deepfake detection framework that integrates face detection, CNN-based feature extraction, and graph neural networks (GNNs). Faces are detected using YOLOv8, cropped, and encoded into discriminative embeddings via pretrained CNN backbones (EfficientNet-B0, DenseNet121, ResNet-50, Xception). These embeddings are organized into a dynamic similarity graph, where nodes represent faces and edges capture cosine similarity among top-K neighbors. GraphSAGE and Graph Attention Networks (GAT) are employed to exploit inter-face relationships, enhancing node representations for collective Real/Fake classification. The YOLO–CNN–GNN pipeline enables scalable and principled detection of deepfakes in images containing multiple faces, surpassing limitations of independent face-level classification. Figure 2 illustrates the overall pipeline

Figure 2. Overview of the proposed graph-based multi-face deepfake detection framework.

4 Experimental result

In this section, we discuss the results and their implications.

Table 1 presents the evaluation of different CNN backbones combined with GraphSAGE and GAT on the deepfake-and-real-images dataset. GAT-based models consistently outperform GraphSAGE, with EfficientNet-B0 + GAT achieving the best performance: 96.77% accuracy and 97.18% F1-score, highlighting its ef-

Metrics	GNN Architectures							
	GraphSAGE(SAmpLe and aggreGatE)				GAT(Graph Attention Network)			
	DenseNet121	EfficientNet-B0	ResNet-50	Xception	DenseNet121	EfficientNet-B0	ResNet-50	Xception
Accuracy (%)	91.12±0.82	92.76±0.91	89.01±0.36	95.15±2.56	94.89±1.36 (↑4.13%)	96.77±0.93 (↑4.32%)	94.29±1.01 (↑ 5.93%)	95.73±0.53 (↑0.61%)
Precision (%)	91.44±1.88	91.63±1.48	87.04±0.85	94.34±4.37	92.33±1.89 (↑0.97%)	95.10±1.63 (↑3.79%)	94.87±1.54 (↑ 9.00%)	95.47±1.99 (↑1.20%)
Recall (%)	92.90±2.90	97.84±1.00	94.40±1.46	97.23±0.40	99.13±0.35 (↑6.71%)	99.27±0.25 (↑1.46%)	94.95±1.96 (↑ 0.58%)	97.04±1.61 (↓0.20%)
F1-score (%)	92.11±0.84	93.68±0.74	90.56±0.36	95.74±2.13	95.60±1.22 (↑3.79%)	97.18±0.78 (↑3.74%)	94.89±0.09 (↑ 4.78%)	96.21±0.43 (↑0.49%)

Table 1. Training performance of CNNs Backbones and GNN architectures on the deepfake-and-real-images dataset.

fectiveness for deepfake detection. EfficientNet-B0 also leads among GraphSAGE models, while Xception + GAT shows competitive results. In contrast, ResNet-50 + GraphSAGE performs the worst. Overall, the results underscore the importance of attention mechanisms and confirm that EfficientNet-B0 combined with GAT is the most robust and accurate configuration.

Based on the comparative analysis, EfficientNet-B0 consistently outperforms the other CNN backbones across all evaluation metrics, particularly when combined with the GAT architecture. It achieves the highest accuracy and F1-score while maintaining stable standard deviations, indicating robust and reliable performance. Due to its superior results, EfficientNet-B0 is selected as the backbone for subsequent experiments.

Operation	GNN Architectures							
	GraphSAGE				GAT			
	Accuracy(%)	Precision(%)	Recall(%)	F1-Score(%)	Accuracy(%)	Precision(%)	Recall(%)	F1-Score(%)
Training	99.71±0.20	99.86±0.15	99.56±0.38	99.71±0.20	99.77±0.28 (↑0.06%)	99.85±0.12 (↓0.01%)	99.85±0.17 (↑0.29%)	99.77±0.27 (↑0.06%)

Table 2. Training performance comparison of GNN architectures on the FaceForensics++ Extracted Faces dataset.

Table 2 reports the training performance of the GraphSAGE and Graph Attention Network (GAT) architectures on the FaceForensics++ Extracted Faces dataset. Both models achieve very high training scores across all evaluation metrics, indicating effective learning of discriminative representations. GraphSAGE reaches an accuracy and F1-score of $99.71\% \pm 0.20$, with precision and recall exceeding 99.5%, demonstrating strong convergence. GAT achieves slightly higher training accuracy and F1-score, both at 99.77%, with a marginal gain in precision (0.01%) but a notable improvement in recall (0.29%), suggesting a stronger ability to correctly identify manipulated samples during training.

Table 3 compares the test performance of GraphSAGE and GAT on the Face-

Source Dataset	Operation	GNN Architectures							
		GraphSAGE				GAT			
		Accuracy(%)	Precision(%)	Recall(%)	F1-Score(%)	Accuracy(%)	Precision(%)	Recall(%)	F1-Score(%)
FaceForensics++	Test	89.09	89.45	89.06	89.25	92.66 (↑4.01%)	91.00 (↑1.74%)	94.98 (↑6.66%)	92.95 (↑4.15%)
Deepfake-and-real-images	Test	82.84	87.66	76.46	81.68	88.23 (↑6.51%)	95.49 (↑8.94%)	82.50 (↑7.90%)	87.21 (↑6.75%)

Table 3. Test performance comparison of GNN architectures on different datasets.

Forensics++ and Deepfake-and-real-images datasets. The results show a clear performance advantage for GAT, highlighting its superior generalization capabilities. On FaceForensics++, GAT improves accuracy to 92.66% and F1-score to 92.95% compared to GraphSAGE, with the largest gain observed in recall (↑6.66%), indicating better detection of manipulated samples. This advantage is even more pronounced on the Deepfake-and-real-images dataset, where GAT achieves substantial improvements across all metrics, demonstrating strong robustness under cross-dataset evaluation.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed approach, we compare its performance with several existing deepfake detection models, as reported in Table 4.

Paper	Dataset	CNN-based	Accuracy Training	Accuracy Test
[6]	[2]	EfficientNet	76.24%	70.9%
[1]	[2]	EfficientNet	99.31%	91.67%
[4]	[8]	CNN	–	88.33%
Our Model	[2]	EfficientNet	99.77%	88.23%
	[3]		96.77%	92.66%

Table 4. Performance comparison of the proposed method with state-of-the-art deepfake detection models

Overall, the findings confirm that attention-based graph modeling significantly enhances generalization performance in deepfake detection. Combined with EfficientNet-B0, GAT provides a more reliable and robust framework, outperforming GraphSAGE especially in terms of recall and F1-score, and proving its effectiveness in handling dataset variability.

5 Conclusion

This paper presents a graph-based framework for multi-face deepfake detection that goes beyond traditional single-face analysis by explicitly modeling interactions between faces. By representing faces as graph nodes and applying relational reasoning, the approach captures semantic dependencies missed by standard CNN-based detectors.

The combination of CNN feature extraction and attention-based graph neural networks allows effective integration of local facial features with global inter-face relationships, resulting in consistent performance gains, especially in cross-dataset evaluations. These results show that relational modeling provides a more robust and generalizable solution for deepfake detection.

Overall, this work demonstrates the potential of graph-based architectures for analyzing manipulated visual content in realistic multi-face scenarios and opens new directions for relational and structured deepfake analysis.

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